

Deliverable D7.3.7.1 Social Media Strategy

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Social Media Strategy NFDI4Energy

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General Information

Summary

This document outlines the primary objectives of our social media activities. It identifies and analyzes the intended audience for our communication efforts, selecting the most effective platforms and methods to reach them. Additionally, we analyze strategies of other consortia to improve our approach. We present a detailed content plan, covering the creation, scheduling, and distribution of content across selected channels. Methods and metrics for tracking the performance of our social media strategy are specified. Finally, we detail strategies for adjusting and refining the communication plan based on performance data and feedback.

Deliverable within NFDI4Energy

The first objective of NFDI4Energy (Nieße et al., 2022) includes the goal of motivating the use of the services of NFDI4Energy in the energy research community. To achieve this goal a good outreach strategy is needed to reach out to the researcher so energy researcher in Germany know about NFDI4Energy and its services. Nowadays, social media is an important outreach channel. Therefore, this deliverable presents the social media strategy of NFDI4Energy. The strategy describes the goals of the consortium's social media activities, details on how to perform them and on how to report important key performance indicators.

Deliverable

Deliverable D7.3.7.1 comprises the social media strategy of NFDI4Energy. A Social Media Marketing Strategy (SMMS) is defined as “an organization’s integrated pattern of activities that, based on a careful assessment of customers’ motivations for brand-related social media use and the undertaking of deliberate engagement initiatives, transform social media connectedness (networks) and interactions (influences) into valuable strategic means to achieve desirable marketing outcomes” (Li et al., 2021, p. 54).

Accordingly, the presented social media strategy aims to achieve its goals by targeting the right audience, selecting appropriate communication channels, learning from other successful initiatives, developing a comprehensive content plan, continuously monitoring performance, and adapting and optimizing our approach.

Goals

With its social media activities, NFDI4Energy works towards the following goals:

- Form internal and external identity of the NFDI4Energy consortium, as a strong, unified identity will strengthen the consortium’s cohesion and public perception
- Support cultural change in energy research data management as a basis for adaptation and implementation of a FAIR mindset and processes.
- Make NFDI4Energy known as relevant service provider for RDM services in the energy domain.

Target groups

With its social-media-activities, NFDI4Energy wants to target the following high-level groups, as described in NFDI4Energy’s Consortium Proposal (Nieße et al., 2022):

1. Researchers active in energy (systems) research
2. Energy-related industry
3. Policy
4. Society

Choice of Communication Channels

Kaplan and Haenlein (2010) describe Social Media in Marketing context as platforms on which people build networks and share information and/or sentiments. They furthermore describe six categories of social media: Collaborative projects, blogs, content communities, social networking sites, virtual game worlds, and virtual social worlds (Kaplan & Haenlein, 2010). Currently, NFDI4Energy is present in collaborative projects (GitHub), content communities (Zenodo) and on social networking sites (LinkedIn). Since the content generation in the first two categories is mainly community driven, once the consortium is set-up on the respective platform, we will subsequently focus the social media strategy of NFDI4Energy on the category “social networking sites”. In this category active content creation and maintenance through NFDI4Energy representatives is necessary.

Channels in this category used by other NFDI consortia are LinkedIn, Mastodon, X, BlueSky. NFDI4Energy is present at LinkedIn and was present at X until December 2023. Due to the increase in disinformation and hate content on X since the owner changed in 2023, many former users had left the platform (Jeong et al., 2024; Reuter, 2023). Leaving X or Staying on the platform has also been

discussed in the NFDI Kommunikationskreis¹ at the end of 2023, resulting in a collective departure from the platform of nine NFDI consortia (one more had already left, three plan to leave in 2024, seven were still indecisive in December 2023). NFDI4Energy was one of the consortia leaving X for ethical reasons in December 2023.

The remaining three platforms used by NFDI consortia are compared in Table 1 in order to decide, if social media activities should be expanded or shifted to other channels.

	LinkedIn	Mastodon	BlueSky
Launched in	2003	2016	2021
Characteristics	professional networking platform focused on career development, industry news, and thought leadership; known for its ability to facilitate professional connections, provide industry-specific content, and enhance personal and organizational branding; text-driven; growing network	decentralized social networking platform that operates on a federated model, allowing users to join different instances (servers) based on their interests and preference; emphasizes user privacy and community-driven content, offering a customizable experience without central control or algorithms dictating content visibility; text-driven; growing network	decentralized social networking platform focusing on user privacy and control, allowing individuals to manage their own data and interactions without central authority; aims to provide a user-friendly experience with innovative features, promoting transparent communication while prioritizing user autonomy; text-driven; growing network
Audience	Professionals, researchers, academics, industry (experts), organizations in the energy sector and related fields, politicians, graduates	General public, tech enthusiasts, open-source community	General public, tech enthusiast
Privacy and control	Controlled by LinkedIn (Microsoft)	User-controlled, data spread across instances	User-controlled, decentralized
Strengths	Professional credibility, large user base, integrated analytics	Decentralization, strong community focus	Decentralization, innovative features, privacy focus
Source	(LinkedIn Corporation, 2024)	(Mastodon gGmbH, 2024)	(Bluesky, 2024)
NFDI Consortia on platform ²	14	16	5

Table 1: Comparison of Social Networking Platforms used from NFDI Consortia

Choosing the right medium for the given purpose strongly depends on the targeted groups. Via LinkedIn NFDI4Energy is able to reach and get in contact with researchers, industry representatives,

¹ Within the NFDI Kommunikationkreis outreach and communication coordinators of all NFDI consortia come together and discuss outreach related topics.

² Reported on May 17, 2024 via <https://www.nfdi.de/konsortien/>.

and politicians, thereby covering the target groups that are decisive for the starting phase of NFDI4Energy. While Mastodon and BlueSky offer unique advantages, such as decentralization and enhanced privacy, LinkedIn's professional focus, larger user base, provided performance metrics, and robust networking features make it a more effective platform for promoting and managing the social media activities of a research project. Hence, NFDI4Energy will firstly focus on LinkedIn as the leading social media channel, since it guarantees reaching those target groups relevant for the starting phase of NFDI4Energy, and will later on assess expanding the social media activities to further channels.

The target group "Society" is not forgotten and will be addressed as the consortium's vision, mission and services are carved out more clearly and thereby can be communicated more tangibly. Currently, appropriate events for informing society are already discussed within Task Area 2 that guarantee better approachability for society than social media communication.

Using LinkedIn as primary social networking platform supports the aforementioned goals of NFDI4Energy's Social Media Strategy as follows:

Increase NFDI4Energy's social media followers on LinkedIn	<i>LinkedIn's professional user base aligns with NFDI4Energy's target audience, making it an ideal platform to grow a relevant follower base through targeted content and engagement</i>
Form internal and external identity	<i>LinkedIn's emphasis on professional branding helps NFDI4Energy establish a cohesive and credible identity both internally among team members and externally to the wider community</i>
Support cultural change	<i>By sharing industry best practices, success stories, and thought leadership articles, LinkedIn can be used to promote and support cultural change within the community and among its stakeholders</i>
<i>Table 2: LinkedIn's accordance with NFDI4Energy's social media goals</i>	

Learning from other consortia

To get an idea of what successful social media channels look like and how they should be managed, we take a closer look at successful initiatives working towards the same goal as NFDI4Energy, but in different disciplines.

We first rank the initiatives based on the number of followers:

Consortium	Followers on LinkedIn ³	Funding Round	Discipline
BERD@NFDI	934	2	Social sciences
GHGA	710	1	Life sciences
NFDI4Chem	700	1	Natural sciences
NFDI4Cat	693	1	Natural sciences
NFDI4Health	553	1	Life sciences
NFDI4Objects	507	3	Social sciences
NFDI4Energy	462	3	Engineering sciences
FAIRmat	462	2	Natural sciences
MatWerk	441	2	Engineering sciences
NFDI4Biodiversity	260	1	Life sciences
NFDI4Microbiota	127	2	Life sciences

³ Recorded on May 17, 2024.

NFDI4Earth	119	2	Natural sciences
NFDI4DS	115	2	Engineering sciences
NFDI4Ing	88	1	Engineering sciences
KonsortSWD	69	1	Social sciences
<i>Table 3: Followers on LinkedIn of NFDI Consortia</i>			

For the following consortia we could not find a LinkedIn account: NFDI4Culture, NFDI4memory, Text+, Matwerk, NFDI4CS, DataPlant, FAIRagro, NFDI4Immuno, NFDI4Bioimage, Daphne4NFDI, MaRDI and Punch4NFDI.

The next step is to take a closer look at the three initiatives with the highest number of followers, namely, NFDI4Chem, GHGA and BERD@NFDI.

Name	NFDI4Chem
SM Platform	LinkedIn
Number of Followers	700
Categories of Content	Repost Spokesperson, repost other Consortia, Announcement/invitation lecture format, announcement event presence, update on meetings of representatives, align with other activities (connect to other channels), report on other projects, teasers of content from website, Announcement of Workshops, talks, events; offer of RDM Workshops, infographic (how to FAIR)
Frequency of Publication	22 posts in the last 3 month (including 7 reposts with comment) -> 1,8 Post /week
Content with best Performance	How to infographic (25 likes) Report about FAIR article (27 likes) Explanation of Open and FAIR + link to website (18 likes)
Cooperation with other Initiatives	Joint event, cooperation on data management plan
Most important Insights	Use reposts (!), very few emojis, reposts of own posts with headline REMINDER, use infographics and content contributions, one "own" post + 1 repost per week is a good frequency
<i>Table 4: Learning from other initiatives LinkedIn activities: NFDI4Chem</i>	

Name	GHGA
SM Platform	LinkedIn
Number of Followers	710
Categories of Content	Advertising its podcast, job advertisement, announce lecture series, announce online course/webinar, report on scientific advancement, content for campaign day (earth day), reposts, announcement of blog article, update from consortia: new member/content, announcement of events
Frequency of Publication	23 Posts over 3 Months (including 8 reposts) 1,9 Posts/week
Content with best Performance	Repost: update on project work (63 likes) Repost: report on mentioning of partner institution in European news (49 likes) Repost: Call for project proposal (39 likes) Repost: Update from other consortium (34 likes)

Most important Insights	put more effort into reposting, active reposting of other (related) consortia’s postings and partner institution’s postings, one “own” post + 1 repost per week is a good frequency, few but high-quality posts work well
<i>Table 5: Learning from other initiatives LinkedIn activities: GHGA</i>	

Name	BERD@NFDI
SM Platform	LinkedIn
Number of Followers	934
Categories of Content	Job advertisement, announcement of talks, call for participation, webinar, challenge for students, conference announcements, slides shared, repost EOSC talks, NFDI talks, conference updates, video from conference venue
Frequency of Publication	49 Posts over 3 Months (including 21 reposts) 4 Posts/week
Content with best Performance	Report on workshop (17 likes) Reposted: Success stories (32 likes) Announcement of student challenge (25 likes) Announcement of presence at conference and chocolate (28 likes)
Cooperation with other Initiatives	Repost of related consortia’s post
Most important Insights	Also repost initiatives outside the NFDI (EOSC), offer more workshops (probably easier in the 3 rd year), include video if possible
<i>Table 6: Learning from other initiatives LinkedIn activities: BERD@NFDI</i>	

The Insights from this analysis will be used for the development of the content plan, presented in the following chapter.

Content Plan

The manner in which NFDI4Energy communicates is characterized by friendliness, accessibility, and clarity. Furthermore, NFDI4Energy orientates towards Kaplan and Haenlein’s advice on how to behave on social media: Be active, be interesting, be humble, be unprofessional, be honest (Kaplan & Haenlein, 2010). Given the negative connotation of the adjective “unprofessional”, we substitute this through “approachable”, thereby trying to align their advice with our self-conception, without compromising on their original statement.

From an interview with a marketing professional from OFFIS e. V. we got the following advice for the usage of LinkedIn:

- Best time for Posting is from Monday to Thursday in the mornings
- Communicate humanely and not too scientifically
- every additional line is good, long articles push reach, the longer people stay on a post, the better
- try to include a personal note/person in postings, they make others interested.

We will use a “Redaktionskalender” summarizing upcoming events, dates of publication of the newsletter, and further reasons for social media postings and containing the planned posts headlines for the current year. The frequency of postings is aimed to be weekly. Based on the planned headlines the postings are elaborated and finalized in the week before their planned publication. The

Redaktionskalender will be updated annually in October of each year for the upcoming period (1.1.-31.12.).

To guarantee regular postings NFDI4Energy uses different types of templates. The templates are subdivided into three themes: Event-posts, Series, and other.

For events we have prepared three templates that can be used by NFDI4Energy representatives to report before, from and after an event. They are accessible for the whole consortia and are actively provided by the outreach coordinator, if an event is upcoming. Not all events provide enough content for three posts: For events where NFDI4Energy representatives only participate or give a presentation, we only use the after-event template. For events with major contributions of NFDI4Energy representatives during the preparation (for example the annual NFDI4Energy Conference), we use all three templates. The postings regarding event participation support the approachability of NFDI4Energy, since they make the consortium’s presence, contributions and insights transparent to the community.

The templates for the category Series are described in the table below:

Name of the Series	Description	Contributes to
TA introduction	Structured presentation of the seven TAs	Forming an internal and external identity
Introduction of partner institution	Structured presentation of all partner institutions of NFDI4Energy	Forming an internal and external identity
Introduction of services (infographics)	Structured presentation of the NFDI4Energy Services	Describe the How and What of NFDI4Energy’s efforts
Introduction of persons	Structured Presentation of persons working in NFDI4Energy	Forming an internal and external identity
Introduction of related consortia	Structured presentation of other consortia that NFDI4Energy works with or that are thematically related (Engineering sciences)	Growing the network and reach of NFDI4Energy

These templates are used to guarantee regular postings on the NFDI4Energy LinkedIn channel and additionally provide content for the quarterly NFDI4Energy Newsletter.

The templates of the category ‘other’ are described in the table below:

Name of the Template	Description	Contributes to
Update from the consortium	Template that is used irregularly to report on progress of the consortia’s work	Updating the community, forming an internal and external identity
Why RDM	Template that is used irregularly when required to highlight the necessity of NFDI4Energy’s efforts	Supporting cultural change
Newsletter	Announces the publication of the latest Newsletter	Updating the community

Templates of the category ‘other’ are used when required.

In addition to the planned posts and connecting to the insights from the analysis of other consortia’s activities, NFDI4Energy will actively monitor the postings of related consortia, partner institutions,

relevant publications, and persons within NFDI4Energy to find repostable content, thereby increasing its reach and visibility.

Channels to be monitored for suitable content for reposts are:

Overarching organization:

- NFDI: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/nfdi-de/>
- Base4NFDI: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/base4nfdi/>
- EOSC: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/eosc-a/>

Related Consortia:

- NFDI4Cat: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/nfdi4cat/>
- NFDI4DataScience: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/nfdi4ds/about/>
- NFDI4Ing: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/nfdi4ing/>
- Matwerk: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/nfdi-matwerk/about/>
- KonsortSWD: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/konsortswd/>
- NFDI@BERD: <https://www.linkedin.com/school/berd-nfdi/>
- NFDI4Earth: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/nfdi4earth/>

Further consortia with strong LinkedIn Channels:

- GHGA: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/the-german-human-genome-phenome-archive/>
- NFDI4Chem: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/nfdi4chem/>

Reposts combined with own text segments are counted as own reach by LinkedIn. Every account has only a limited amount of reach. Therefore, it is advised to combine reposts with own text if in the same week no post with own content is planned, and to repost without text, if in the same week own content is posted.

Furthermore, building on the insights of the analysis of other consortia’s work, it is planned to include more content and results from the consortium into the communication via LinkedIn, to increase the number of valuable content and educational contributions. It is assumed that this will become easier within the 3rd year of the consortium, once the first interim results are achieved.

Monitoring and Analysis

Since we only have limited time resources for our social media activities, we want to focus our efforts on pushing content rather than on extensive reporting. Nevertheless, the performance of NFDI4Energy’s social media activities on LinkedIn will be tracked through the following Key Performance Indicators (KPIs):

	Key Performance Indicator	Reporting Frequency	Current status (Q2/2024 aggregated)
KPI1 – Content	Impressions (focus indicator)	Quarterly	Impressions: 4561 (570,125 /Posting) Unique impressions: 2691 (336,375 /Posting)
KPI2 – Follower	Followers	Quarterly	+ 50 (0,55/day) 30.06.2024: 484 Follower
KPI3 - Visitors	Number of Visitors	Quarterly	Total page views: 162 Total unique visitors: 70
KPI3.1 – Visitors Location	Location of visitors	Yearly	Greater Oldenburg Area, Germany 55 (37,67%) Greater Karlsruhe Area, Germany 29 (19,86%) Greater Dresden Area, Germany 9 (6,16%) Paderborn, Germany 7 (4,79%)

			Greater Munich Area, Germany 6 (4,11%) Hannover-Braunschweig-Göttingen-Wolfsburg Region, Germany 5 (3,42%) Frankfurt Rhine-Main Area, Germany 5 (3,42%) Grand Tunis Metropolitan Area, Tunisia 4 (2,74%) The Oldenburg Munsterland, Germany 4 (2,74%) Other 22 (15,07%)
KPI3.2 – Visitors Job	Job function	Yearly	Research 89 (69,53%) Education 11 (8,59%) Administrative 9 (7,03%) Business Development 8 (6,25%) Community and Social Services 3 (2,34%) Human Resources 2 (1,56%) Operations 2 (1,56%) Engineering 2 (1,56%) Sales 1 (0,78%) Entrepreneurship 1 (0,78%)
KPI3.3 – Visitors Industry	Industry of visitors	Yearly	Research Services 51 (33,33%) Higher Education 30 (19,61%) IT Services and IT Consulting 25 (16,34%) Renew. Energy Equipment Manuf. 14 (9,15%) Manufacturing 5 (3,27%) Civil Engineering 4 (2,61%) Government Administration 4 (2,61%) Financial Services 3 (1,96%) Oil and Gas 2 (1,31%) Other 15 (9,8%)

The KPIs can be extracted from NFDI4Energy’s LinkedIn profile and should be downloaded and edited quarterly. The KPIs will be presented bi-annually to the Coordination Office (January and July). Necessity and design of measures will be discussed in these meetings. Also, goal metrics for each KPI will be determined in these meetings for the following period as well as what KPIs will be presented in the upcoming consortium meeting.

Adaptation and Optimization

This social media strategy will be audited annually in June by the Outreach Coordinator. The audit’s results shall be presented to the Coordination Office in the aforementioned meeting.

The audit’s leading questions are:

- How have the KPIs developed over the last year? What does this tell us?
- What content categories(/channels) work well? Which do not?
- Which are the strongest contributions?
- Who do we interact with? Which are our most successful cooperations?
- Do we still reach the targeted groups via our social media channel(s)?
- Should we expand our strategic social media activities on further channels?
- How do we perform in social media activities compared to other initiatives?
- What trends, chances and risks arise?

The results of the audit will be summarized in a brief report.

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